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**Shape of Faculty Development for
Tomorrow – Implications for Theory,
Practice & Scholarship**

Abstract Book

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Relationship among gratitude, optimism, and emotional exhaustion of health sciences teachers

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Background

A lesson from the COVID-19 pandemic is the importance of having a faculty capable of managing and responding to their emotional and social needs and those of their students. In stressed situations having faculty with high levels of gratitude and optimism helps to maintain an atmosphere of confidence and to hope for the best for the future, academically, socially, and personally. There are indications that this may serve as a coping strategy for emotional exhaustion, particularly for teaching exhausting times.

Summary Of Work

This is a quantitative study of cross-sectional design. In it participated 205 health professionals who teach at a private university in northeastern Mexico. The data analysis consisted of Pearson's product-moment correlation test (r) with a 90% confidence interval determined by bootstraps. The variables studied are gratitude, optimism, and emotional attrition.

Summary Of Results

Participating teachers report high levels of gratitude ($M= 3.49$, $SD= .48$, $min= 1.83$, $max= 4.0$) and optimism ($M= 2.39$, $SD= .46$, $min= 1.25$, $max= 3.0$), while emotional exhaustion is

medium low ($M= 1.53$, $SD= .99$, $min= 0.0$, $max= 4.0$). Gratitude was found to be positively associated with optimism ($r= .36$, $p< .001$, $95\% CI [.22, .48]$) and negatively associated with emotional exhaustion ($r= -.28$, $p< .001$, $95\% CI [-.13, -.42]$); as for optimism and exhaustion, a negative relationship was found ($r= -.45$, $p< .001$, $95\% CI [-.33, -.56]$).

Discussion And Conclusion

Promoting gratitude and optimism in the faculty promotes self-efficacy, facilitates the adoption of new institutional models and strategies, and generates greater institutional identity. We found that optimism has a stronger relationship with emotional exhaustion, while gratitude was more distal. This leads to continuing with the study of positive teacher emotions as protective factors against burnout.

Take Home Messages

Since promoting positive emotions in health professors directly impacts the teaching-learning process, it has a positive effect on their relationships with their patients and loved ones. Educational institutions should establish policies for the human flourishing of their faculty.

